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Effect of Youtube-Video-Learning Strategy on Performance in Algebra Concepts among Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the effects of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on the performance in Algebra among senior secondary school students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study adopted a pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design with a single experimental group. The population comprised of 4,001 SS2 Mathematics students from 22 public senior secondary schools during the 2024/2025 academic session in Funtua Educational Zone. A sample of 88 students was selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught Algebra instruction using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, while there was no separate control group as the study focused on the effects within the experimental group only. The Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data. The instrument was validated by experts at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and had a reliability coefficient of 0.70, calculated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated. Data analysis involved calculating the mean, standard deviation, and mean difference to answer the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using paired sample t-test at a 0.05 significance level. The findings showed no significant gender-based differences in performance within the experimental group. Based on the results, the study concluded that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are effective for improving performance in Algebra and are gender-neutral. It is recommended that secondary school mathematics teachers incorporate YouTube Video-Learning Strategy in teaching complex concepts like Algebra.

Key words: YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, Algebra, Academic Performance

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Introduction

Mathematics is taught at various educational levels in Nigeria, including the basic, secondary, and tertiary levels, and is considered essential in many aspects of life, as noted by Olanrewaju (2023). De Vera and Balgua (2023) describe Mathematics as the foundation and essence of science and technology. In Nigeria, the formal education system plays a critical role in imparting scientific and mathematical knowledge, developing essential skills, shaping attitudes, and fostering a mindset that values science, particularly Mathematics. Blåsjö (2021) views Mathematics as the cornerstone of all true sciences, asserting that no scientific field can thrive without mathematical principles. Agah (2020) emphasizes the interconnection between Mathematics, science, and technology, stating that without Mathematics, science would not exist, and without science, technology would be impossible—ultimately leading to the absence of modern society. As a result, Mathematics is universally recognized as a core subject, taught in every country around the world, although the language of instruction may vary depending on the official language of each nation (Acharya, Kshetree, Khanal, Panthi, & Belbase, 2021).

Hillmayr, Ziernwald, Reinhold, Hofer, and Reiss (2020) emphasized that Mathematics is a crucial tool for the advancement of science and technology. A nation cannot develop scientifically and technologically without prioritizing the teaching and learning of Mathematics, as it is fundamental for understanding and interpreting concepts in these fields. The National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) recognizes Mathematics as a core subject, mandating that all students, regardless of their discipline, gender, or ability, must study and pass it at a credit level, particularly at the secondary school level. To achieve the goals of Mathematics education, Nigeria, as a developing country, requires modern innovations in teaching and learning processes, which necessitate skilled mathematicians who can help realize these goals. Despite the critical role of Mathematics in development, studies by Ndidi and Effiong (2020) and Eyong, Ugada, and Aminu (2020) show that Nigerian students often perform poorly in Mathematics, citing factors such as lack of teaching materials, Mathematics anxiety, ineffective teaching methods, and inadequate teaching facilities, including equipment and instructional resources. To address these challenges, researchers such as Pattier (2021) and Nabayra (2022) have recommended the use of modern teaching methods, including YouTube videos.

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According to Maziriri, Gapa, and Chuchu (2020), YouTube videos are valuable educational tools that stimulate student engagement and enhance learning by allowing for repetitive viewing, enabling students to fully grasp the concepts being taught. Pratama, Arifin, and Widianingsih (2020) highlighted the influence of television and video materials on learners, noting that they enrich classroom experiences with resources that may not typically be available in traditional settings. Mayer (2021) noted that instructional videos do more than present factual information; they illustrate and contextualize it, enhancing students' understanding by providing visual and auditory elaborations. This combination of sound and images strengthens students' retention of key information. Similarly, Alpizar, Adesope, and Wong (2020) found that the use of multiple sensory channels and rich elaboration of information supports learning and aids in the retention of verbal information. Additionally, Moreno-Guerrero, Rodríguez-Jiménez, Gómez-García, and Ramos Navas-Parejo (2020) emphasized that instructional videos in education are designed to achieve specific objectives, which should positively influence students' attitudes toward learning. According to scholars, Video-Learning Strategy can make learning more permanent and offer valuable experiences for students. When used effectively, Video-Learning Strategy can significantly enhance students' academic performance.

Academic performance is typically measured by the quality of students' test or examination scores, especially in comparison to other students at the same level. Jomuad and Paclipan (2020) describe academic performance as the scholarly standing of a student at a particular point in time. Wang, Hofkens, and Ye (2020) define academic performance as the result produced by students, reflected in the quality of their examination scores. Similarly, Ariastuti and Wahyudin (2022) suggest that academic performance is an indicator of how much a student has learned. Another key variable in this study is gender, which is defined as a set of characteristics that distinguish between males and females (Shahzad, Hassan, Aremu, Hussain, & Lodhi, 2021). Depending on the context, these distinguishing characteristics can range from biological sex to social roles to gender identity. Siddiqi and Shafiq (2017) view gender as a socio-cultural construct that assigns specific roles, attitudes, and values deemed appropriate for each sex. Research by Rodriguez, Regueiro, Piñeiro, Estévez, and Valle (2020) highlights that gender is an important factor influencing academic performance in Mathematics. They argue that the belief that Mathematics is a subject primarily for boys can result in lower motivation among girls, contributing to a wider gender gap in Mathematics achievement, with boys performing better. This disparity often leads to

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lower performance in Mathematics and Mathematics-related subjects among female students. The present study seeks to investigate whether a difference exists in the performance of male and female SS II students in the Funtua Education Zone when taught using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

The research study draws upon Dual Coding Theory (DCT), a cognitive framework developed by Allan Paivio in the 1960s. DCT suggests that humans process and represent information both verbally and non-verbally, with mental imagery playing a crucial role in the formation of memory (Paivio, 1991). According to Paivio's theory, the development of verbal understanding is heavily reliant on a strong non-verbal foundation, with both systems working in tandem to process linguistic and visual information. In the context of investigating the impact of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on algebra performance among senior secondary school mathematics students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria, DCT offers valuable insights into how students assimilate mathematical concepts. The incorporation of visual tools such as YouTube videos allows educators to engage both verbal and non-verbal cognitive systems, potentially enhancing students' understanding and retention of algebraic principles. The theory's emphasis on mental imagery aligns with the use of multimedia resources, which have been shown to facilitate learning, especially in abstract subjects like algebra (Reiber, 2000). Additionally, by considering the range from concrete to abstract in knowledge representation, educators can adjust their instructional materials to match students' cognitive preferences, thus potentially improving their performance in algebra. This application of DCT highlights its relevance in educational settings and its potential to inform teaching practices aimed at maximizing student learning outcomes.

Statement of the problem

In recent years, the integration of technology in education has been heralded as a means of enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in abstract and challenging subjects like algebra. However, there is a growing concern regarding how gender differences may influence the effectiveness of technology-based learning tools, such as YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, in secondary school mathematics education (Aliyu, Tijjani & Usman, 2025). Despite the increasing use of multimedia tools in classrooms, limited research has explored how these resources impact male and female students differently, especially in terms of their academic performance in algebra. In

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the context of Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria, the existing educational strategies may not fully address the potential of digital resources to engage both male and female students equally. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the effects of YouTube video-based learning resources on the performance of male and female senior secondary school mathematics students in algebra. The problem lies in the gap in knowledge regarding whether these resources contribute equally to improving algebra performance across genders, or whether they have a differential impact on male and female students. This study aims to address this gap and provide insights into how gender might influence the efficacy of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy in enhancing algebra performance among secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

1. Examine the effect of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on performance of SS II Mathematics students in algebra by gender.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study;

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female SS II students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

Methodology

The research design for this study is quasi-experimental, utilizing a pre-test, post-test approach with an experimental group. The study involves only one experimental group, where YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are used to teach algebra, with no

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control group in the analysis. Two intact classes, one designated as the experimental group and the other as the control group, were selected for the study.

The target population for this study includes all SS2 students from 22 public senior secondary schools in the Funtua Educational Zone of Katsina State, with a total of 4,001 students. This group is composed of 2,050 male students and 1,951 female students, with an average age of 17 years. The population includes 18 co-educational schools and 4 single-sex schools, two of which are male-only and two are female-only, all managed by the Katsina State Government. The schools are either day schools or boarding schools.

To select the sample, multi-stage sampling technique was employed. A total of 88 SS2 students were selected as the study sample from one public co-educational school in the Funtua Educational Zone. For data collection, the researcher utilized a single instrument, the Algebra Performance Test (APT), which was created specifically for this study. The APT consists of 40 multiple-choice questions derived from algebra topics, using a table of specifications based on Bloom's taxonomy (1970). The test was evaluated for construct, criterion, and content validity by professors from the Department of Science Education at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Before the main study, the instrument underwent pilot testing at Kurami Government Senior Secondary School, which is part of the larger population but not included in the sample. A group of 30 students from this school participated in the pilot testing. Following the pilot, the data was analyzed to determine the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of the APT was calculated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS Version 20.0, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.70. This result indicates a strong positive correlation between the initial and subsequent administrations of the test, demonstrating that the instrument is reliable for the study.

Presentation of Results

Results obtained from the data collected were analyzed as follows:

Research Question One: What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy?

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To answer the research question two post test scores from APT for experimental and control groups were subjected to mean and SD. Summary of the findings is in Table 1.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics of Posttest APT scores for Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

GENDER	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference
Male	51	34.59	1.63	0.39
Female	37	34.19	1.87	

Result of the descriptive Mean statistics showed that there is no difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. Their computed mean performances are 34.59 and 34.19 of Male and female SSII Secondary school Mathematics students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy respectively. This shows that both male and female students have the same level of mean performance when taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy

Testing Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

To test null hypothesis two, the post test scores from APT for male and female of the experimental group were subjected to independent sample t-test. The summary is presented in Table 2.

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Table 2: Summary of Independent Sample t-test of Mean Posttest APT Scores for Male and Female in Experimental Group.

GENDER	N	Mean	STD	Mean diff.	Df	T comp.	t crit.	p
Male	51	34.59	1.63	0.39	86	1.07	1.96	0.289
Female	37	34.19	1.87					

P > 0.05, t-computed < 1.96 at DF 86

Result of the independent t-test statistics showed that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. Reasons being that the calculated p-value of 0.289 is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the computed t-value of 1.07 is lower than 1.96 t-critical value at df 86. Their computed mean performances are 34.59 and 34.19 of Male and female SSII Secondary school Mathematics students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy respectively. This shows that both male and female students have the same level of mean performance when taught with students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, is hereby accepted and retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students when exposed to YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. This suggests that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are a gender-neutral tool in terms of their impact on academic performance, as both male and female students benefited equally from the intervention. This outcome aligns with the research conducted by Khan, Saeed, Anwar, and Kanwal (2023), who found that boys did not outperform their female counterparts in heterogeneous group settings. Similarly,

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Onasanya et al. (2022) and Sharma (2024) found in their independent studies that gender did not have a significant impact on student performance when video-based resources were used as instructional tools. These findings suggest that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy can serve as an inclusive and effective teaching strategy for all students, regardless of gender.

However, contrasting results were observed in the study by Kutigi et al. (2023), where male students outperformed female students in various areas when exposed to flipped classroom instructional models. The differences in findings between this study and the one by Kutigi et al. (2023) may stem from the different instructional approaches used in each study, with flipped classrooms potentially providing more opportunities for male students to excel. It is important to note that these discrepancies underscore the importance of considering instructional methodologies and their varying effects on students across genders.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the use of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy significantly enhances the academic performance of both male and female students, demonstrating that these resources are gender-neutral. The study revealed that YouTube video-based learning not only provides a more engaging and interactive method of teaching algebra but also fosters equal participation and achievement among male and female students. This suggests that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy offer a flexible and accessible learning platform that accommodates the diverse learning styles of students, irrespective of gender. The positive impact on both male and female students' performance highlights the potential of technology-based tools like YouTube videos to bridge any gender-based gaps in educational outcomes, offering a more inclusive approach to teaching complex subjects such as algebra. Therefore, it is recommended that educators incorporate YouTube Video-Learning Strategy regularly into their teaching strategies to improve student engagement and learning outcomes, benefiting all students regardless of gender.

Recommendations

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1. School administrators should invest in providing adequate technological infrastructure, including internet access and multimedia tools, to ensure that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy can be effectively integrated into the teaching of Algebra and other mathematical concepts.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to develop and share a repository of quality YouTube Video-Learning Strategy that align with the curriculum, enabling students to access supplementary learning materials beyond the classroom and reinforce their understanding of algebraic concepts.
3. Educational stakeholders, including the Ministry of Education, should promote the use of YouTube video-based learning as part of the national curriculum, advocating for its adoption as a valuable tool for improving students' comprehension of challenging mathematical topics and encouraging gender-equitable learning environments.

REFERENCES

- Acharya, B. R., Kshetree, M. P., Khanal, B., Panthi, R. K., & Belbase, S. (2021). Mathematics Educators' Perspectives on Cultural Relevance of Basic Level Mathematics in Nepal. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 12(1), 17-48.
- Agah, M. P. (2020). Challenges of mathematics in economic development in the twenty-first century: Implications for tertiary education. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 33(3), 20-25.
- Alpizar, D., Adesope, O. O., & Wong, R. M. (2020). A meta-analysis of signaling principle in multimedia learning environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(5), 2095-2119.
- Ariastuti, M. D., & Wahyudin, A. Y. (2022). Exploring academic performance and learning style of undergraduate students in English Education program. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 3(1), 67-73.
- Blåsjö, V. (2021). Galileo, Ignoramus: Mathematics versus Philosophy in the Scientific Revolution. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.06595*.
- Bloom B. S. (1970). Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, *Handbook I: The Cognitive Domain*. New York: David McKay Co Inc.
- De Vera, M. C., & Balgua, B. L. O. (2023, May). Utilization of technologies in teaching mathematics in a flexible learning environment. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2602, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
- Eyong, E. I., Ugada, C., & Aminu, A. (2020). Indicators of Improved Achievement of Students' in Mathematics. *The Universal Academic Research Journal*, 2(1), 29-37.
- Hillmayr, D., Ziernwald, L., Reinhold, F., Hofer, S. I., & Reiss, K. M. (2020). The potential of digital tools to enhance mathematics and science learning in

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- secondary schools: A context-specific meta-analysis. *Computers & Education*, 153, 103897.
- Jomuad, P. D., & Paclipan, M. O. (2020). Relationship between family and school factors and the students' academic performance in mathematics. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*.
- Khan, A., Saeed, M., Anwar, M. N., & Kanwal, L. (2023). Unleashing the Potential: A Study of the Effectiveness and Impact of YouTube Educational Content on Student Learning outcomes. *Journal of Mass Communication & Journalism*, 13(5), 1-9.
- Kutigi, U., Gambari, I., Tukur, K., Yusuf, T., Daramola, O., & Abanikannda, O. (2023). Gender differentials in the Use of flipped Classroom Instructional Models in enhancing achievement and Retention in oral-english contents of senior secondary School in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Humanities Research*, 2(2), 1-21.
- Mayer, R. E. (2021). Evidence-based principles for how to design effective instructional videos. *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 10(2), 229-240.
- Maziriri, E. T., Gapa, P., & Chuchu, T. (2020). Student perceptions towards the use of YouTube as an educational tool for learning and tutorials. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(2), 119-138.
- Moreno-Guerrero, A. J., Rodríguez-Jiménez, C., Gómez-García, G., & Ramos Navas-Parejo, M. (2020). Educational innovation in higher education: Use of role playing and educational video in future teachers' training. *Sustainability*, 12(6), 2558.
- Nabayra, J. (2022). Mathematics learning in the new normal through teacher-created videos: The freshmen university students' experience. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities Studies*, 2(1), 22-27.
- Ndidi, M. A., & Effiong, I. E. (2020). Influence of Classroom Environment on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Calabar Nigeria. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 15(8), 495-503.
- Olanrewaju, S. S. (2023). Mathematics Education in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. *Rethinking the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in the Pandemic Era*, 176.
- Onasanya, T. O., Aladesusi, G. A., Taiwo, S. A., Onasanya, S. A., & Adeoye, J. T. (2022). Effect of technology-enabled video instruction on senior secondary school students' performance in selected technical drawing concept in Ilorin. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 2(2), 141-148.
- Pattier, D. (2021). Teachers and YouTube: The use of video as an educational resource. *Ricerche di Pedagogia e Didattica. Journal of theories and research in Education*, 16(1), 59-77.
- Paivio, (1991) Dual Coding Theory: Retrospect and Current Status, *Canadian Journal of Psychology* 45,255-287

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- Pratama, S. H. H., Arifin, R. A., & Widianingsih, A. W. S. (2020). The use of Youtube as a learning tool in teaching listening skill. *International Journal of Global Operations Research*, 1(3), 123-129.
- Rodriguez, S., Regueiro, B., Piñeiro, I., Estévez, I., & Valle, A. (2020). Gender differences in mathematics motivation: Differential effects on performance in primary education. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 3050.
- Sharma, G. (2024). Investigating the Influence of YouTube Educators on Academic Achievement: A Study of Teenagers Preparing for Competitive Exams. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 4(2).
- Shahzad, A., Hassan, R., Aremu, A. Y., Hussain, A., & Lodhi, R. N. (2021). Effects of COVID-19 in E-learning on higher education institution students: the group comparison between male and female. *Quality & quantity*, 55, 805-826.
- Siddiqi, N., & Shafiq, M. (2017). Cultural value orientation and gender equity: a review. *Social Psychology & Society*, 8(3).
- Wang, M. T., Hofkens, T., & Ye, F. (2020). Classroom quality and adolescent student engagement and performance in mathematics: A multi-method and multi-informant approach. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 49, 1987-2002.
- Aliyu, Z., Tijjani, R. A., & Usman, M. H. (2025). Assessing the Role of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Enhancing Algebra Performance among Senior Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State. *ATBU Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 13(1), 131-138.